

Deliverable D2.3

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Project Acronym:	BioMedBridges	
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Deliverable title:	Definition of a user-centered design process with the technical work packages	
WP No.	2	
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WP Title	Outreach and inreach	
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WP leader:	Deborah Alfarez	13: VUMC
Contributing partners:	N/A	

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1 Executive summary

This deliverable proposes a set of guidelines for use by the technical workpackages, enabling them to employ a user-centred design approach to development of their services.

User-centred design (UCD) is an approach to design that focuses the design process on the needs of the people who will actually use the product.

The purpose of this deliverable document is not to provide a pre-defined “recipe” for UCD for the BioMedBridges end-products; rather, we hope to:

- stimulate discussion of how UCD could be incorporated into the project;
- bring all partners to a shared understanding of the importance of UCD in the planning, design and evolution of BioMedBridges services for end-users;
- share useful resources for UCD.

2 Project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives:

No.	Objective	Yes	No
1	Ensure the promotion and dissemination of BioMedBridges deliverables to its stakeholders	X	
2	Specify the expectations, motivations and requirements of stakeholders and their inter-relationships with the BMS infrastructures concerning the implementation of common solutions.	X	

3	Involve the stakeholders, including end users, patient organizations and industrial stakeholders, in informing the outcome of the BioMedBridges deliverables.	X	
4	Provide strategic outreach to other projects and relevant initiatives (including the individual BMS RIs and e-Infrastructures, relevant IMI projects and EMBL-EBI Industry Programme) to support the implementation of the common solutions developed by BioMedBridges.	X	

3 Detailed report on the deliverable

3.1 Background

The goal of BioMedBridges is to make it easier for basic, translational and clinical researchers to work with the data bridges and access huge amounts of biomedical data with the aim to use these data to make discoveries that will enhance the health of European citizens. These users will have to change their everyday workflow at the bench, or in the clinic and are therefore an extremely important target group for engagement. Not only do we need to inform them of new services that will enhance their research capability; we also need to involve them, from an early stage, in the development of these services. We should also strive to understand the workflows that our audience follows, so that the services we produce better fit in with and support them.

By incorporating strategies for user-centered design into BioMedBridges, we will be able to “complete the circle” between developers and users, thereby making it more straightforward to develop services that balance the needs of the users with the goals of the service providers. This deliverable proposes a set of guidelines for use by the technical work packages, enabling them to employ a user-centred design approach to development of their services.

We anticipate that this approach will be most applicable to the browser-based infrastructure for data integration specified in WP4; it may also be applicable to the products of other work packages, for example, D7.7 – sample discovery tool for mouse models integrated with EMBL-EBI and MUG resources; M9.6 – prototype of web-based segmentation and identification service (integrating structural data); and D10.3 – prototype federated query interface (integrating disease-related data and terminology from different sample types).

3.2 Definition of user-centered design process with technical work packages

3.2.1 What is user-centred design?

User-centred design (UCD) is an approach to design that focuses the design process on the needs of the people who will actually use the product. It is part of an international standard - ISO 9241 “Ergonomics of human-system interaction”.

EMBL-EBI has successfully used UCD in the design of a number of projects with functionality related to that which we ultimately have in mind for the BioMedBridges browser-based services – the European Genome-Phenome Archive (EGA - <http://www.ebi.ac.uk/ega>), EBI search (available from www.ebi.ac.uk/ and all EBI sub-pages) and the Enzyme portal (www.ebi.ac.uk/enzymeportal).

UCD has been successfully applied to design in many different domains, although its application to bioinformatics services (de Matos et al., submitted; Pavelin et al., 2012), and to related fields such as medical informatics (Viitanen, J., 2009) is relatively recent. The case for using UCD for bioinformatics services is compelling: even major bioinformatics resources are known to suffer from usability problems (Javahery et al., 2004), and usability problems are known to prevent users from completing tasks (Bolchini et al., 2009). We therefore see the incorporation of UCD into the development of the BioMedBridges services as an opportunity to gain maximum return on the EU’s investment in BioMedBridges,

and on the ESFRI member states' investment in the biomedical science research infrastructures.

Although, compared with traditional software design processes, UCD can require a longer time span between the start of the project and developing the software, the decision-making process at each stage is simplified because it is guided by clear requirements from users, leading to reduced load on developers and better end results. The UCD process often also generates physical artefacts that can be used to inform and sanity check the technical specification - the focus is not on deliverables but on tools that help to focus the design effort. Finally, the involvement of different types of stakeholder in the design process from the earliest stages helps to build a sense of community and shared purpose.

There is no single recipe for success in user-centred design; often, the different phases of the design process occur in parallel and some development may already have taken place before a project has a tightly defined product specification. The purpose of this deliverable document is not to provide a pre-defined “recipe” for UCD for the BioMedBridges end-products; rather, we hope to:

- stimulate discussion of how UCD could be incorporated into the project,
- bring all partners to a shared understanding of the importance of UCD in the planning, design and evolution of BioMedBridges services for end-users, and
- share useful resources for UCD.

3.2.2 Design is a process

A useful reference guide, developed by the Design Council through research on how successful companies manage the design process, is available at <http://www.designcouncil.org.uk/designprocess>. It includes the following visualisation of the design process (Figure 1):

Figure 1 The “double diamond” of the design process, as described by the Design Council

It divides the whole design process into two main phases (represented as two diamonds), each with a divergent and convergent section. Although they are labelled differently in this image, we could call the first one the “problem phase” and the second one the “solution phase”. Essentially, we want to be sure of what we are trying to achieve before we start developing solutions.

We have found this a useful way to frame the design process in a number of our projects, and we will refer to it in the next section.

3.2.3 Proposal for the BioMedBridges UCD process

Development process

Phase 1: Discover - understanding the problem

The first phase of design is typically divergent and exploratory, and takes place at the start of a project. The purpose is to define who your audience is, what their overall goals are, how your project is going help your audience achieve these goals, and how it will fit into the workflows of the audience.

Who are our users?

BioMedBridges WP2 is gathering information on the stakeholders of each of the research infrastructures participating in the project (D2.2, stakeholder analysis). We hope that, among other things, this stakeholder analysis will contribute towards user research. There may be a tension between designing for the naive user (new or infrequent user – in the case of BioMedBridges likely to be represented by experimental researchers, laboratory animal scientists or clinical investigators) and designing for the power user (in the case of BioMedBridges likely to be represented by bioinformaticians or biomedical informaticians).

We propose designing the BioMedBridges federated access system for the naive user, partly because it will then also be usable by more experienced users, and partly because there will be other products (e.g. the programmatic access infrastructure) aimed at power users. This will lower the barrier to acceptance and broaden the appeal of the services we provide.

How does BioMedBridges fit in?

No matter how unique, user friendly and powerful the software that is ultimately produced, it is still likely to be only one part of a more complex workflow based on solving a research problem. This idea of fitting into a flow is an important aspect of user-centred design.

As an analogy, imagine that John is planning to go on a hike. He is unlikely to define the workflow for planning his route as “I’m going to use Google maps today”. Furthermore, we wouldn’t expect Google maps to enable him to do all his planning; he might need to book rail tickets to get him to the start of his hike, or find restaurant recommendations en route, for example (see Figure 2).

Figure 2 Simple linear workflow, using an everyday example

Similar principles apply to the use of bioinformatics tools, so it may be helpful to think of the BioMedBridges federated access system as one tool in a broader workflow.

Figure 3 Simple linear workflow involving the BioMedBridges federated access system at one stage. Understanding how users need to fit BioMedBridges into their workflows will help to define the technical specification for BioMedBridges user interfaces

To provide an illustrative example, a researcher may have a question such as “drug A was unsuccessful in a clinical trial although there were some good responders; what distinguishes the responders from the non-responders?” (see Fig 3). The researcher may use a variety of tools work towards an answer to this question; in our example, the BioMedBridges federated access system may be used to compare the genotypes of the trial subjects and find out whether any SNPs distinguish the responders from the non-responders. Other resources, including confidential, patient-specific information or proprietary information on genotype-phenotype interactions may be used to gather further information.

Defining which part of our users' workflows BioMedBridges can expedite, and which parts are better addressed by other tools, is a key part of ensuring that BioMedBridges will fit seamlessly into their workflows.

Phase 2: Define - what are we making, and for whom?

In this phase of the design process, we would typically begin to converge ideas and research, so that we know what we are aiming to build and for whom. This allows us to generate requirements, align project and user goals, and move into the development phase with confidence.

In our experience, structured workshops provide an excellent way to help project teams clarify what they are going to work on. It is particularly useful to involve developers and other stakeholders in this so that we can understand any constraints or opportunities.

There are also methods we can use here to define the audience, and thus guide later development work (see Appendix 2).

Phase 3: Develop - make and test

Once we have explored and defined the problems we want to solve, the workflows we want to support, and the services we wish to provide, we can begin to develop solutions.

Typically, we begin by exploring a range of solutions in a lightweight, iterative way, so that we can give ourselves options for solving the design problems we are dealing with. A variety of prototypes, wireframes or mockups can be assessed and validated against what we learned in the Discover and Define phases of the design process. We strongly recommend that project teams explore interface and interaction concepts using pen and paper to start with. This is fast, cheap and collaborative, and means that teams can hopefully avoid getting stuck on one coding route. Methods that are particularly useful here include the use of personas, scenarios and usability testing, both of which are described in Appendix 1. This open approach allows us to maintain a focus on the user, and thus make this a user-centred design process.

In creating prototypes, we need to think about interface design and interactivity, the transitions from one interface or tool to another, and again, how things fit into a workflow.

Having evaluated and tested a divergent range of concepts, we need to begin to converge on what we want to code and build.

Phase 4: Deliver - solutions and validation

The final stage of the design process that we will consider is the delivery of a product. Having explored and tested a range of design concepts, we can focus on what we know works, and take something into production (i.e. full coding and development of a service), taking into account the constraints that we are working under (time, funds, human resources, etc.).

Delivery does not end with launch of the interface: observing usage and modifying the interface in light of usage should become an ongoing part of the development cycle so that the BioMedBridges user interface will continue to evolve in line with users' needs. It is easy to fall prey to 'feature creep' at this stage; checking your refinements against the original technical specification and against user requirements can help to allay this risk.

Recognising a hierarchy of needs

By carrying out user research, and understanding how to balance user and project goals, we can be confident about the utility of our products. Later in the design process, when we begin to code these products, we would of course ensure functionality. By exploring possibilities, testing concepts and prototypes, and allowing ourselves to "fail early", we can design for usability, allowing our users to get tasks done using our products. Ultimately, we might aspire towards making our products desirable, so that they are the preferred choice of researchers.

Figure 4 Illustration of using the design process to build up from a product or service that is simply useful, to one that is desirable (based on Maslow's hierarchy of needs)

This can only be built on a solid foundation, though, and taking a user-centred approach to the design process can help us achieve that.

References cited

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Pavelin, K. et al. (2012) Bioinformatics meets user-centred design A Perspective.

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Snyder, C. (2003) *Paper prototyping: the fast and easy way to design and refine user interfaces*. Elsevier

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4 Publications

N/A

5 Delivery and schedule

The delivery is delayed: Yes No

6 Adjustments made

The scope of the deliverable was slightly adjusted to better reflect the needs of the project. The previous title “Definition of a user testing process with technical work packages” was changed to “Definition of a user-centred design process with the technical work packages”.

7 Efforts for this deliverable

Institute	Person-months (PM)		Period
	actual	estimated	
1 EMBL-EBI	1	1	September 2012
Total	1		

We anticipate that it will take approx. 1 person-month's worth of work to complete steps 1 and 2 of the process proposed above; thereafter we will incorporate the remainder of this process into our outreach and training activities as far as possible.

Background information

This deliverable relates to WP2; background information on this WP as originally indicated in the description of work (DOW) is included below.

WP2 Title: Outreach and inreach
Lead: Deborah Alfarez (VUMC)
Participants: VUMC

BioMedBridges is an ambitious and complex project, the success of which will depend on outreach to a diverse group of stakeholders. These range from bench researchers, software developers through biomedical researchers at all stages of the medicines research and development pipeline. WP 2 will contribute to the successful implementation of BioMedBridges by coordinating targeted inreach and outreach activities.

Inreach activities will ensure that the BioMedBridges participants share a common vision on the aims of the software solutions implemented by the technical work package. For example, it will ensure that user requirements and user testing scenarios are embedded into the project from the very beginning.

Outreach activities to various stakeholder groups, including software developers, end-users of the BioMedBridges services and Patient groups, will raise awareness of the solutions developed in the technical work packages. Our strategy will include making the most of our links to the individual BMS RIs to communicate with these stakeholder groups on our behalf. BioMedBridges' outreach activities will play a key role in assuring that BioMedBridges is seen as a trustable party (for example, by the patient who has the right to determine who is using his data, or the bench researcher who might need to change aspects of his day-to-day work when using solutions developed by BioMedBridges).

Work package number	WP2	Start date or starting event:	Mo 1
Work package title	Outreach and inreach		
Activity Type	COORD		

Participant number	13: VUMC	1: EMBL	5: UDUS
Person-months per participant:	40	2	2
Objectives			
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. To ensure the promotion and dissemination of BioMedBridges deliverables to its stakeholders. 2. To specify the expectations, motivations and requirements of stakeholders and their inter-relationships with the BMS infrastructures concerning the implementation of common solutions 3. To involve the stakeholders, including end users, patient organizations and industrial stakeholders, in informing the outcome of the BioMedBridges deliverables. 4. To provide strategic outreach to other projects and relevant initiatives (including the individual BMS RIs and e-Infrastructures, relevant IMI projects and EMBL-EBI Industry Programme) to support the implementation of the common solutions developed by BioMedBridges. 			
Description of work and role of participants			
<p><i>Task 1: Stakeholder definition and stratification (M1-M6)</i> (Leader: VUMC, Participants: UDUS, EMBL-EBI)</p> <p>BioMedBridges is an ambitious and complex project, the success of which will depend on outreach to a diverse group of stakeholders. These range from bench researchers, software developers through biomedical researchers, both in academia and in industry, at all stages of the medicines research and development pipeline.</p> <p>Definition of these groups, and identification of appropriate strategies for engaging and training with each group in a targeted way, will be key to the success of the project. Through consultation with (i) project partners, (ii) the communications teams of the BMS Research infrastructures, (iii) other e-Infrastructure projects (iv) industrial stakeholders e.g. via the IMI project EMTRAIN and (v) our advisory board we will define stakeholders as a first step towards developing a communication strategy. Stakeholder groups can broadly be divided into:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> (1) technical personnel in the BMS-RIs and e-infrastructures; (2) end-users of the BMS RIs (ranging from basic researchers through to physicians, other professionals involved in clinical trials and industry representatives); (3) patient organisations. <p>(1) Software developers (EMBL-EBI): sharing of expertise in data integration and software interoperability will be an important part of BioMedBridges, as it brings together developers from diverse application domains with different cultures; for example, the medical informatics, bioinformatics and cheminformatics</p>			

communities have very different models for the development and implementation of standards. 'Inreach' to the project partners will be an important goal in this respect. We will also need to communicate with technical personnel involved in the BMS RIs but not in this project. Technical personnel in related EU-funded projects, including INFRA-2011-1.2.1: e-Science environments, INFRA-2011-1.2.2: Data infrastructures for e-Science and INFRA-2011-1.1.7. Life sciences bio-molecular data resources and services represent a third target group, of great importance if Europe is to gain maximum benefit from its investment in e-Science infrastructure.

(2) End-users of the BioMedBridges services (EMBL-EBI, VUMC, UDUS). The immediate goal of BioMedBridges is to make it easier for basic, translational and clinical researchers to work with the data bridges and access huge amounts of biomedical data with the aim to use these data to make discoveries that will enhance the health of European citizens. These users will have to change their everyday workflow at the bench, or in the clinic and are therefore an extremely important target group for engagement. Not only do we need to inform them of new services that will enhance their research capability; we also need to involve them, from an early stage, in the development of these services. Outreach to our users will therefore need to include strategies for user testing.

We will do this by organising a workshop with representatives of the technical work packages during the first year of the project, to agree on a process for user testing and to identify appropriate subjects for user testing.

To ensure that BioMedBridges successfully implements the access to cutting edge e-technology platforms for academia and industry, the end user stakeholders that will be defined and stratified in task 1 and for which an outreach plan will be developed in task 2 will include industrial stakeholders. For this amongst others contacts to IMI Knowledge management projects will be used and if necessary established. In addition in order to reach its target with respect to industrial stakeholders, namely to create an improved environment for translation to industry and commercial exploitation of data a close interaction will be established with WP3 to ensure cross-fertilisation when identifying key industry players in the standardisation arena across the involved disciplines. Patients' Organisations (VUMC, UDUS). BioMedBridges' impact will be seen through expediting research, the ultimate goal of which will be improved health of Europe's citizens, especially in terms of better healthcare and improved treatments. As BioMedBridges will develop architectures for data sharing that will also include sensitive patient data, the involvement of patient organisations will be a crucial factor for the acceptance, dissemination and overall outcome of the project. Because patients must consent to the use of their data and samples for research, the involvement of patient organisations will advance the project's aims to improve data exchange. We will invite an appropriate representative to join the BioMedBridges advisory board and will work with this representative to ensure that BioMedBridges builds trust among all groups involved in BioMedBridges.

Task 2: Creation of inreach and outreach plans (M6-M48)

(Leader: VUMC, Participants: UDUS, EBI)

In this task, we will develop a plan to involve the stakeholders defined in task 1. Again, the involvement of our advisory board members and those of the BMS research infrastructures will be important. The plan will be split into two phases. In years 1 and 2 the focus will be on establishing awareness with stakeholders relevant to WPs 3-5 about BioMedBridges and its goals. These stakeholders include industrial stakeholders as described in task one. The outreach plan to the industrial stakeholders will make use of the link to the IMI Knowledge Management projects as well on the existing EBI/ELIXIR industry programme. The second phase (years 3 & 4) will be based on systematically informing stakeholders about the solutions implemented within BioMedBridges.

Phase 1 will need to include a plan for 'inreach' to the BioMedBridges partners and to their collaborators in the BMS RIs. Each of the partner infrastructures is itself a large and distributed 'organisation' so good communication with these scientists is non-trivial and will require effort and commitment. It will be necessary to raise awareness in these communities of the e-science approach as a new way of working, introducing the ideas of in-silico labs and multi-disciplinary, cross organizational collaboration among all BMS-RIs. This will include establishing a common understanding of the goals and the methods for achieving these goals, at all levels of participants within the BMS-RIs.

Phase 2 will need to include resources for travel to conferences to promote adoption of BioMedBridges standards, best practices and tools, and for publishing the achievements of BioMedBridges in the Scientific, Technical and Medical press. Much of this will be done in the individual infrastructures, and this work package will take steps to ensure that key messages from the project are communicated by the individual BMS RIs. The final AGM of BioMedBridges will be open to all stakeholder groups and will include a programme aimed at celebrating the deployment of robust data bridges and services promoting interoperability between the BMS RIs with all our stakeholders.

Task 3: Development of a BioMedBridges brand and supporting materials (M6-M18)

(Leader: VUMC, Participants: EMBL-EBI)

We will support the BioMedBridges partners to promote the infrastructures developed by BioMedBridges by managing the development of a logo, PowerPoint and poster templates, key messages, press releases and a regular project bulletin. A BioMedBridges website and newsletter will disseminate the supporting material. We will work closely with the BioMedBridges project manager, who will be responsible for managing the project website, to achieve these goals.

Deliverables

No.	Name	Due month
D2.1	Initial basic branding, including logo, power point and poster templates	2
D2.2	Definition and segmentation of stakeholders	6
D2.3	Definition of user testing process with technical work packages	9
D2.4	Development and implementation of outreach plan for different stakeholder groups	36
D2.5	Final AGM – meeting and report	48

Appendix 1: Useful resources

Design Council – the design process

<http://www.designcouncil.org.uk/designprocess>

This site summarises the process used by successful companies to design their products. The model presented emphasises the point that the initial phases of the design process (discovery and definition) are as resource intensive as the later phases (development and delivery).

Usability Net

<http://www.usabilitynet.org/home.htm>

An EU-funded project providing resources to improve usability and promote user-centred design in other EU projects. The methods table helps developers to identify appropriate methods on the basis of resources available and the stage of the project.

EBI Interfaces blog

<http://ebiinterfaces.wordpress.com>

A forum for developers and designers of websites, interfaces and visualisation tools aimed at life scientists.

UX for Devs Manifesto

http://www.infragistics.com/community/blogs/ambrose_little/archive/2012/07/01/ux-for-devs-manifesto.aspx

An article published in July 2012 by “design technologist”, Ambrose Little, provides a neatly explained manifesto aimed at developers, and describes the importance of their role in the design process.

Don't Make Me Think (Krug)

ISBN: 0321344758

Written in an accessible, jargon-free way, this is perhaps the quintessential book for introducing ideas about usability and designing for good user experience in development projects.

Universal Principles of Design (Lidwell, Holden, Butler)

ISBN: 1592535879

This updated and revised version offers “115 Ways to Enhance Usability, Influence Perception, Increase Appeal, Make Better Design Decisions and Teach Through Design”.

Prototyping (Warfel)

ISBN: 1-933820-21-7

The practitioner’s guide to prototyping, it compares and describes methods for prototyping designs in a range of media, from paper to Powerpoint, and from Fireworks to HTML/CSS.

Appendix 2: Explanation of UCD terminology and methods

Mockups, wireframes and prototypes for visual communication

When we begin to develop solutions to a given design “problem”, it is particularly effective to visually communicate what we understand about user requirements and project goals. Mockups and wireframes allow us to show, rather than simply tell, while functional prototypes allow us to go to the next level, and to experience and more accurately test the actual use of a product.

Mockups

Mockups are essentially pictures of how an interface might look in a given state. They can be either of low-fidelity (even paper & pen) images or high-fidelity, pixel-perfect images.

Wireframes

Wireframes are a tool that allow us to explore information hierarchy and layout on pages. They communicate functional page structure.

When shown in sequences, they also allow us to think about interaction, and the transition from one interface [state] to another. They are normally annotated so that they can be shared with team-members. They are also usually deliberately devoid of visual styling (except typography and text-sizing), so as not to distract the reader.

Prototypes

Prototypes are models of the final product, and allow developers and users to experience their use, rather than just showing it.

They might use very minimal code (just enough to allow interactivity); they can be created in software like Powerpoint or Keynote, allowing us to “fake” interactivity to quite a high degree; they might be simple “paper prototypes” that allow us to explore simulated interaction.

For an excellent guide to prototyping, and descriptions of pros and cons, please see the book “Prototyping”, referenced in Appendix 1.

Personas & scenarios

A commonly-used technique to help guide decision-making throughout a design is the use of “personas”. These are user archetypes, based on data and research, who represent key parts of your target audience.

Personas have two important functions. Firstly, they can help to guide decisions about the functionality of the product under development: we can ask questions such as “how might the removal of functionality A affect the workflow of User B?”. Secondly, they can create empathy, reminding the developer that the user may have different end goals than their own. Some example personas are provided in Annex 1.

WP2 could support the other workpackages to develop and refine these profiles if this is deemed desirable. For example, we could develop personas to represent each of the BioMedBridges use cases by interviewing technical leads from each of the use cases, developing draft personas, then asking each of the use case workpackage leaders to provide contact details for users who are representative of these draft personas. Interviews with these individuals could be used to refine our personas further.

Figure 5: an example of one of the personas used in the EBI website redesign project

Personas can be brought to life when they are placed in scenarios - short stories that explain context-of-use, situation, goals, and so on. If you have had the time to carry out some user research, and build a picture of your users, you will have a rich source of material for these scenarios, and your personas can be really put to work.

Personas are valuable if they are referred to throughout the UCD process to sanity check the product specification, design and delivery of the product. They are of limited utility if they are used for the initial product spec and then put to one side.

Usability testing

Assuming we have useful, functional prototypes and products, we want to assess their ease-of-use, too.

Usability testing allows us to discover usability issues, i.e. problems with the interface (including its content) that prevent a user performing a given task, or at least, make it very difficult.

Usability testing should involve participants who represent members of your target audience (if you have personas, they can be helpful in selecting participants). Observe as they perform tasks using your prototypes, and note any clear usability issues that arise. Tasks should be representative of what that participant might really do, and should ideally take place in a representative context.